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Work Package 6

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Project Deliverable

D6.4: Demonstrator of integration of wearable sensors

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Executive Summary

This document describes the demonstrator of integrating wearable Ultrasonic Personal Air Samples (UPAS) sensors derived abiotic or biotic data output within the Human Exposome Assessment Platform (HEAP) Hopsworks platform. The Hopsworks platform provides both batch and streaming ingestion and analytics capabilities, which are used within the presented demonstrator. The demonstrators use the notebook computation environment for development and exploration and then switch to pipelines and scheduled jobs once the code is developed and goes into production. The demonstrators take full advantage of the new capabilities to fully customise the computation environments. The primary research and development of pipelines is performed by partners from Stanford University and Oulu University (UOULU) and implemented in the CSC computational cloud with the support of the Hopsworks team.

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1. Introduction

1.1 Purpose

This document extends on the demonstrator D6.3, which showcased the Data Analytics and Machine Learning (ML) capabilities of the Knowledge Engine of the HEAP Hopsworks platform. This demonstrator also presents the streaming capabilities of Hopsworks. Hopsworks integrates with Kafka as an event streaming source. It can come with its own internal Kafka service but can also integrate with existing Kafka clusters.

1.2 Overview

This document presents capabilities of the HEAP Hopsworks platform that are outcomes of the following ongoing tasks:

- Task 6.3: Data warehousing has as an outcome:
 - the improvements to the management of the virtual computing environment
 - the development of the storage layer for easy access to the data from all forms of computing (notebook or jobs).
 - integrations for easy sharing, searching and collaboration.
- Task 6.4: Data streaming from IoT - improving the platform's capabilities to connect to streams of events through Kafka and analysing these streams using Spark streaming of Flink.
- Task 6.5: Deep learning on Heap data; there has been collaborative work between Hopsworks and medical partners to implement the pipelines within the Heap Hopsworks platform.

1.3 Structure of the document

The structure of this document is as follows:

- **Section 1** (this section) introduces the document, its purpose and a list of acronyms and abbreviations.
- **Section 2** - the background section introduces the basic capabilities of Hopsworks in developing the present demonstrators.
- **Section 3** describes the analysis pipelines from a demonstrator of the HEAP integration of wearable sensors.

2. Background

2.1 Streaming with Kafka

Apache Kafka is a distributed event store and stream-processing platform that established itself as a leading real-time data stream management framework. Its widespread adoption stems from its robust, production-ready capabilities. Frequently deployed as a core service, Kafka efficiently manages the flow of events originating from production systems. These events undergo extensive processing before reaching their ultimate destinations, including loading into a data warehouse or aggregating features tailored for machine learning applications.

When connecting to the Kafka service running in the Heap Hopsworks platform, the user must first define a Kafka storage connector, refer Fig. 1, which is then used to access the Kafka-stored events.

Figure 1: Kafka as a storage connector

The connector details, refer Fig. 2, contain name, description, Kafka bootstrap servers, which security and communication protocols should be used, and additional, optional parameters can be provided in a key-value format.

Set up storage connector

Name 📌 **Description** optional

name of the source description

Protocol

AWS S3 JDBC HopsFS Redshift Azure Data Lake Snowflake **Kafka** ¹ Google Cloud Storage Google BigQuery

Parameters

Bootstrap servers ²

localhost 9091 +

Security Protocol ³

SSL SASL SSL plaintext SASL plaintext

TrustStore **TrustStore password**

KeyStore **KeyStore password**

Key password

SSL endpoint identification algorithm

HTTPS disabled ⁴

Options optional ⁵

key value +

Figure 2: Kafka storage connector configuration.

Starting with version 3.4, Hopsworks brings the capability to connect to external, existing Kafka clusters. Hopsworks thus continues on its path for excellent connectivity with well-known frameworks and an attempt at reducing maintenance efforts and costs. This is a step forward for Hopsworks, being an even more modular platform.

2.2 Fully customisable docker environment

As outlined in previous deliverables, we take full advantage of the fully customisable docker jobs within the demonstrators presented in this deliverable. Starting with version 3.4 docker images, representing the project's environment, are fully customisable. While previous iterations allowed diverse installation modes, focusing primarily on Python libraries, the latest version enables users to install any library, be it system packages, R or C/C++ libraries. (Fig. 3)

Figure 3: Custom library installation.

2.3 Jupyter Notebooks

Once your ingestion is set up and data can be read using the configured storage collectors, you can start exploring the data and figuring out what features you need for your future models and how to best extract them from the streaming data. Developing with Jupyter Notebooks is provided as a service in Hopsworks, for example, in Fig. 4, as part of the compute section of a project.

Figure 4: Running Jupyter Notebooks in Hopworks.

Notebooks are mainly used for exploratory purposes, and once you have developed your analytics code that extracts and aggregates the features you require, you can organise it as a pipeline of jobs and run it on a schedule.

2.4 Feature Store

A feature store is a centralised and potent repository designed to store machine learning features. This innovative platform empowers organisations to seamlessly iterate, reuse, enhance, and govern their machine-learning models and associated data within an open ecosystem. With the flexibility to connect to multiple data sources for ingestion and integrate with various data science tools for serving, the feature store plays a pivotal role in bridging the realms of DataOps and MLOps. It addresses fundamental components of AI infrastructure, providing a solution that harmonises data management and machine learning operations.

3. Demonstrator

We describe some of the work with partners of Stanford University and Oulu University (UOULU) related to the exposome data analysis. We first describe the chemical exposome pipeline, which processes the data collected by wearable UPAS (Ultrasonic Personal Air Sampler) exposometers and an example of how it is implemented in Hopsworks on a sample dataset.

Secondly, we describe our machine learning-based development for the study using synthetic example data from the Finnish population cohort. This work will eventually be deployed to the Finnish wearable UPAS exposometer data (curated pilot data currently in analysis).

3.2 Exposome Pipeline

In the following section, we provide an overview of the chemical exposome pipeline, followed by how a demonstration setup was implemented and run in HEAP Hopsworks. The work overlaps with other deliverables D6.3 and D5.2. In this section, we describe the details of the setup in Hopsworks. Partners from Stanford University, UOULU and CSC carried out the primary research and development of the pipelines described in detail in D5.2.

Research objective

The study primarily aimed to construct a process for detecting components of the biotic and abiotic exposure (i.e. exposome) from samples gathered using a wearable Ultrasonic Personal Aerosol Sampler (UPAS) exposometer. This is a pioneering investigation with significance for Exposome research. Eventually, this investigation aims to assess the significant correlations between chemical exposure and biological effects at the individual level using longitudinal wearable UPAS exposometer data.

Overview

Figure 5: Overview of the Chemical Exposome Pipeline.

This section presents a comprehensive overview of the chemical exposome pipeline's functionality. The pipeline comprises a set of scripts written in shell and R, incorporating automatic parameter optimisation for processing raw LC-MS data through utilising XCMS integrated into MetaboAnalystR. It encompasses tasks such as LC-MS/MS data deconvolution and matching with the Exposomics Database, which includes currently reported compounds related to the exposome.

Searching for hundreds or thousands of chemical compounds within a vast database is a time-consuming and computation-intensive process. Therefore, it is advisable to perform careful parameter optimisation and utilise parallel computation to ensure that the processing time for each sample remains within a reasonable timeframe.

Figure 5 illustrates the initial step in acquiring raw LC-MS data from samples. Subsequently, XCMS integrated into MetaboAnalystR is employed to extract LC-MS data using automatically optimised processing parameters, resulting in the generation of LC-MS feature tables. Following this, LC-MS/MS data undergoes deconvolution and is compared to MS/MS fragments in the Exposomics

Database to identify chemical compounds. Finally, the identified compounds are used to formulate hypotheses regarding the connection between chemical exposure and biological responses.

Dataset

We used Liquid chromatography coupled to mass spectrometry (LC-MS) full scan MS data and data-dependent acquisition (DDA) LC-MS/MS data files from the chemical filters collected by a wearable exposometer. Publicly available LC-MS and LC-MS/MS data files were used as sample data for demonstration setup. As this data is publicly available, we comply with any data sharing and security requirements, which is a constraint when working with private individual data.

This data consists of varied information such as peak details, retention periods, intensity, and fragmentation data that can be utilised to ascertain the molecular weight (expressed as a mass-to-charge ratio or m/z), structure, identity, and quantity of specific chemicals found in the samples. These chemicals are found across all life forms, including humans, microbes, animals, and plants.

Concerning the nature of data from wearable technologies, the data is collected in regular and fixed intervals with a timestamp. This data is processed in batches along with the time stamp.

Programming framework

The Chemical Exposome pipeline comprises a set of scripts written in shell and R. The bioinformatics tools or packages are open-source software primarily developed in C/C++ or R.

The total time required for processing is contingent upon the number of files and the size of each file. Processing a data set derived from 100 samples could potentially take up to 3 days. However, the overall runtime could be significantly reduced by implementing parallel computation during the raw LC-MS data processing and LC-MS/MS data annotation stages, which are the most time-consuming stages in the pipeline.

The pipeline tools utilise CPU, with varying core numbers configured at each pipeline stage for optimal computation. Raw spectral processing requires a minimum of 16GB RAM. Recommended settings for parallel cores are 6 cores for 64GB RAM, 4 cores for 32GB RAM, and 2 cores for 16GB RAM.

Demonstration on the Hopsworks platform

A demonstration of the exposome program in R, complete with a sample dataset, was set up on the Hopsworks HEAP platform. We have incorporated all the system packages and R dependencies into a Docker image to simplify the installation of all dependencies. This approach facilitates the sharing and management of all required dependencies without the hassle of manually installing them. For constructing the Docker image, we utilised the publicly accessible official *r-base*¹ as our

¹ https://hub.docker.com/_/r-base/

base Docker image and layered our dependencies on top of it. An example of a code snippet of the *dockerfile* used to build the docker image is shown in Table 1 below.

```
FROM r-base:latest

WORKDIR tmp

COPY ./Install_dep.R .

RUN apt-get update

RUN apt install libcairo2-dev libnetcdf-dev libxml2 libxt-dev libssl-dev -y

RUN apt install libfontconfig1-dev libharfbuzz-dev libfribidi-dev -y

RUN apt install libpng-dev libtiff5-dev libjpeg-dev -y

RUN apt install pandoc -y

RUN Rscript Install_dep.R
```

Table 1 - Sample of Dockfile used to create a docker image, R packages are installed via R script.

We configure a Job in Hopsworks using Docker to run the program, for example, in Fig. 7. This allows us to run any Docker image in a new container. The path to the R script is provided as an argument to the job, which runs as a command in the Docker container. The required scripts are uploaded to a project dataset first, and the dataset path is given as a job configuration parameter. A high-level overview of the entire workflow to run the exposome pipeline in Hopsworks is shown in Fig. 6. As shown in the diagram; the docker container can transact with the HopsFS, the underlying distributed file system in Hopsworks, for reading/writing input and output files, making it easy for the user to access the data in Hopsworks.

Moreover, once a Job is set up, it can be conveniently scheduled, or any subsequent jobs can be automatically initiated upon completion using the Apache Airflow² integration in Hopsworks. This functionality enables the easy operation of any conditional processes, eliminating the need for users to initiate each job manually.

² <https://airflow.apache.org/docs/apache-airflow/stable/index.html>

Figure 6: Visualization of the workflow to running the abiotic exposome pipeline in Hopsworks as docker containers

Figure 7: Abiotic exposome pipeline docker job configuration.

The running jobs can be easily monitored in the Hopworks UI. An example job run is shown in Fig 8. The total processing time for the job was 127 minutes and was run with 24 GB and 4 CPU cores. More memory and cores can be easily configured by changing the cluster configurations and available resources.

Figure 8: Example of job run and monitoring showing job status and duration

For specifying input and output paths, we can easily mount the input and output dataset directories in Hopworks to the docker container in the job configuration. We mounted an output dataset to a docker job, which we used to generate all the outputs from the script. Thus, output data from the docker container is readily available in the output dataset without any hassle of moving the data between HopFS and local docker container storage. An example of the output files generated by the docker container and directly mounted to the output dataset in Hopworks is shown in Fig. 9.

File Name	Author	Date	Size
file2.txt	Dhananjay Mukhedkar	Oct 29, 2023 2:46:47 PM	0.1KB
Install_dep.R	Dhananjay Mukhedkar	Oct 31, 2023 11:13:33 AM	1.7KB
Rtmp1i860E	Dhananjay Mukhedkar	Oct 31, 2023 11:13:33 AM	-
Rplots.pdf	Dhananjay Mukhedkar	Oct 31, 2023 11:13:33 AM	-
upload	Dhananjay Mukhedkar	Oct 31, 2023 11:13:51 AM	-
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> metaboanalyst_input.csv	Dhananjay Mukhedkar	Oct 31, 2023 10:35:33 PM	960.2KB
annotated_peaklist.csv	Dhananjay Mukhedkar	Oct 31, 2023 10:35:33 PM	1.6 MB
annotated_peaklist.rds	Dhananjay Mukhedkar	Oct 31, 2023 10:35:34 PM	708.3KB
peak_result_summary.txt	Dhananjay Mukhedkar	Oct 31, 2023 10:35:34 PM	0.8KB

Figure 9: Sample output files from R script generated from the docker container

The R script employs an Rmarkdown file for data processing, subsequently saving the comprehensive report and output in the form of an HTML file. A sample report is available in the git repo output³.

Further work

We are currently implementing the final step involved in the pipeline in the Rmarkdown script (MS2, as shown in Fig. 5) in the docker image. The output data generated by the pipelines are mostly CSV format files or can be modified into CSV files. We are working towards improved input data curation for the required abiotic data (i.e. LC-MS/MS data) implementation into the Hopsworks Feature store. This will make it easy to store, access and share the columnar features in the output and make it available for further analysis or as training data for machine learning.

Summary of results/publications

³https://github.com/HEAP-EXPOSOME/exposome-demo/blob/main/output/exp_demo_lc_ms_data_processing.html

We demonstrated how the abiotic exposure pipeline using data from the UPAS exposometer can be run in the Hopsworks HEAP platform. Packaging all the required R dependencies in a docker image makes it convenient for installation and sharing the functionalities for other uses. Also, it is easy to version the docker images if the dependencies installed are changed over time. We can choose the compute cores and memory necessary for running the docker container easily in Hopsworks, as supported by the hardware in the nodes in the CSC cluster. Furthermore, once actual pilot data output is available, we can produce a streaming dataset using the timestamps and ingest it in Hopsworks as though it was streaming data.

The sample reports generated are easily available in Hopsworks datasets folders, which can be further ingested in the Hopsworks Feature Store or simply share the HTML reports. The demo code can be found on git repo⁴. The scientific discoveries of the research with LC-MS samples were partly published in [1,3]. The LC-MS data processing was detailed in [4] and partially utilised in [1,2,5,6].

References

1. *Contrepolis, K. et al, Mol. Cell. Proteomics (2015)*
2. *Goodrich JA, et al., JHEP Reports, 2022*
3. *Goodrich JA, et al., EHP, 2023*
4. *Jasmine C. et al., Bioinformatics (2018)*
5. *Pang, Z. et al. Metabolites 2020*
6. *Lin, X. et al., Metabolites 2022*

⁴ <https://github.com/HEAP-EXPOSOME/exposome-demo>

3.3 Supervised Machine learning

Machine Learning for metagenomic microbial data (UOULU)

This section describes the objective and analysis of applying machine learning techniques in Hopsworks, utilising biotic data obtained from the CSC pipelines described in D5.2 and eventually executed on the wearable UPAS exposometer data. This is done in partnership with Oulu University (UOULU). Subsequent sections provide a detailed description of the ML pipeline, its operations, an overview of the technical components, and finally, the scientific outcomes. The work also overlaps with another deliverable, D6.3, which involved a pilot study using different biotic datasets. The current deliverable expands upon it, incorporating the knowledge gained from it and improvements with an updated dataset and methodologies.

Description

In this study, we utilised supervised machine learning, specifically gradient-boosted trees, to determine individuals susceptible to infection exposure-related cancers. We used clinical and metagenome data from the Finnish population cohort, which was initially processed by the wearable UPAS exposometer pipelines in CSC described in D5.2, and results were then curated into a CSV dataset, which was used as input data for this study. Thus, the study is part of method development for implementing advanced ML analysis on biotic exposure data from longitudinally collected wearable UPAS exposometer data described in D5.1/D5.2/D5.3 of the WP5.

Research question

The study's overall objective was to investigate if it is possible to accurately predict an individual's cancer risk using limited clinical patient description jointly with biotic exposure data of a population cohort from Finland. Moreover, we wanted to test if infection-related cancer prediction models need separate inferences for HPV unvaccinated and vaccinated populations using data previously published and available from the Finnish HPV vaccination cohort [Pimenoff et al. 2023]

Overview

A high-level workflow for the entire data flow is shown in Fig. 10. On the left most side we observe the origin of the data collection, followed by the bioinformatics pipelines in CSC which produce the output data. This curated data is later uploaded into the Hopsworks, and we then utilise it for training models, which finally make predictions. The most important steps and methodology can be broken down into the following subsections:

Figure 10: High-level workflow for data flow from raw data to predictions

Data curation

In our research, we employed HPV genotype, microbial, and other clinical metadata from cohorts within the Finnish population. The data used for training was compiled in a CSV file, which included a distinct sample identifier for each patient, the HPV and bacterial taxonomic identifier, and its relative abundance, which was scaled from 0 to 100. The raw data contained an impressive number of over 120,000 records (n=127116).

To get a glimpse of the data, a sample is shown in Fig. 11. The details of each column are as follows:

- 1) **sample id** - unique identifier for each person (alphanumeric)
- 2) **taxonomic class** - species of bacteria/virus (categorical values from taxonomic classification)
- 3) **relative abundance** - abundance score (float)

The target labels to predict are class A and class B signifying different cancer risk groups in a population

- 1) class A - Individuals with higher risk of developing a particular cancer
- 2) class B - Individuals without risk of developing particular cancer

	sampleId	Taxa	abundance
0	A_101	X.Ruminococcus..gnavus	1.406875
1	A_101	Achromobacter.sp..B7	1.406875
2	A_101	Acidovorax.sp..KKS102	1.406875
3	A_101	Acinetobacter.baumannii	1.406875
4	A_101	Acinetobacter.berezinae	1.406875

Figure 11: Sample of raw CSV data as input.

This data is similar but different compared to what we used during the pilot study as described in deliverable D6.3, which had 3 target classes and different column features, although the nature and source of the data are the same.

We first upload raw data in CSV format to a dataset directory in Hopsworks. The data curation process involves several steps: initially, we load the CSV file into a Pandas⁵ dataframe. We then rename the columns, eliminate the identifier column and pivot table, and execute label encoding to transform the labels into numerical values of 0 and 1. After these transformations, the dataframe consists of 396 rows and 321 feature columns. At this point, we have two target labels that have been label-encoded: class A as 0 and class B as 1. However, the data is imbalanced, with class A (0) having 55 samples and class B (1) having 341 samples. The methodology for addressing this imbalance is discussed in subsequent sections.

Create training data

The data was partitioned into training and test sets, with an 85-15% split, respectively. A further division of the training data resulted in a 10% validation set utilised for cross-validation during model training. Given the limited number of rows (396) and the previously discussed data imbalance issue, synthetic data was generated to mitigate these issues. We employed the Synthetic Minority Oversampling Technique (SMOTE)⁶, a prevalent oversampling method, and its Python implementation to generate additional samples. Post-synthesis, the training set comprised 580 rows with an equal distribution of both class A and B. This approach aids in model training and circumvents overfitting issues. Importantly, the synthetic data was solely derived from the training

⁵ <https://pandas.pydata.org/>

⁶ [SMOTE — Version 0.12.0.dev0 \(imbalanced-learn.org\)](https://imbalanced-learn.org/stable/over_sampling/sMOTE.html)

set to prevent information leakage from the test set, and the model evaluation is strictly conducted on the test set.

Model Training

We used the *XGBoost*⁷ Classifier, a Gradient Boosting tree method, which is shown to perform well on tabular data. Deep learning methods were not utilised due to the data's insufficient size, which could result in overfitting. For the XGBoost model, we implemented cross-validation with a validation set for the tuning of hyperparameters.

The XGBoost model training hyper-parameters were as follows:

```
{  
  'objective': 'binary:logistic',  
  'eval_metric': 'auc',  
  'max_depth': 3,  
  'min_child_weight': 10,  
  'random_state': 113,  
  'reg_lambda': 2,  
  'verbosity': 1,  
  'eta': 0.01  
}
```

Table 2.: Hyperparameters of trained XGBoost model

We also tried training Random Forest models. However, the results on the test sets were not promising as the model was facing overfitting issues. Therefore, we continued the analysis only with the XGBoost model.

All the training and data curation were performed in the Jupyter notebook with a Python kernel with the built-in Jupyter Lab support in Hopsworks. Most of the libraries and Python packages required were already installed in the pre-built Python environment of the Hopsworks project. This makes it easy to focus on development work without the hassle of managing and installing all required dependencies manually.

⁷ <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/XGBoost>

Evaluation on test set

The trained XGBoost model was evaluated on a separate test set for analysing the model performance on unseen data. The test set did not contain any synthetic data but only the actual data. It's crucial that we refrain from using any test data during the training phase to prevent any leakage of test data information into the training data, which could potentially lead to overfitting problems. The key metrics employed for evaluation and maximising the model performance were *F1-score*⁸ and Receiver Operating Characteristic Curve (*ROC AUC*)⁹ score.

Summary of results

We evaluated the trained XGBoost models on the separate test set. We looked at different metrics, for example, F1-score and ROC-AUC score, available from the *scikit-learn*¹⁰ Python package. Table 3 shows the evaluation report for each class, 0 and 1, and its score for precision, recall, F1-score and overall scores. The ROC-AUC plot is shown in Fig. 12. Based on the results, we can conclude that the model can classify between the two classes with reasonable accuracy.

Model	Class	Precision (%)	Recall (%)	F1-score (%)
XGBoost	A (0)	33	78	49
	B (1)	95	73	82
Overall accuracy		73%		
Overall F1-score		76%		
ROC-AUC score		75%		

Table 3. Evaluation report on a test set for XGBoost

⁸ https://scikit-learn.org/stable/modules/generated/sklearn.metrics.f1_score.html

⁹ https://scikit-learn.org/stable/modules/generated/sklearn.metrics.roc_auc_score.html

¹⁰ <https://scikit-learn.org/stable/index.html>

Figure 12: ROC curve of the model evaluation with AUC > 0.7 of the test set.

Further work

Presently, we are in the process of improving model performance and further analysing the results. To enhance the generalisation of the ML models, we are examining the importance of features and conducting feature selection to reduce the feature space in ML inference. Importantly, we are currently applying larger exposure datasets with more patient metadata and a higher quality of viral and deep-sequenced metagenome data compositions as previously described (Pimenoff et al. 2023, Obón-Santacana et al. 2022).

References

Pimenoff VN, Gray P, Louvanto K, Eriksson T, Lagheden C, Söderlund-Strand A, Dillner J, Lehtinen M. Ecological diversity profiles of non-vaccine-targeted HPVs after gender-based community vaccination efforts. *Cell Host Microbe*. 31(11):1921-1929.e3, 2023.

Obón-Santacana M, .., Pimenoff VN, Moreno V. Meta-Analysis and Validation of a Colorectal Cancer Risk Prediction Model Using Deep Sequenced Fecal Metagenomes. *Cancers*. 14(17):4214, 2022.

4. Conclusion

This deliverable D6.4, Demonstrator of integration of abiotic exposure data from wearable UPAS exposometer, presents the efforts undertaken in Task 6.4 - Data streaming from IoT and Task 6.5 - Deep Learning on Heap Data. This demonstrator takes full advantage of Hopsworks' capabilities, including a versatile development environment that can seamlessly jump from Jupyter notebooks used for exploration to schedulable jobs used for production. The project teams, together with the git integration, provide a great environment for collaborative development for data curation and analyses.

A summary has been provided regarding the collaborative efforts of project partners in developing the exposure analyses pipelines used for the wearable UPAS exposometer data, as well as the ML pipelines for advanced inference of biotic exposure (i.e. deep metagenomic microbial data) of the human exposome both described in detail in D.5.2 and D5.3 of the WP5.